
**Six Decades Journey of Professor PK Gupta:
A Legacy in Toxicology, Education, and
Global Scientific Leadership**

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Summary

This article provides an overview of the significant scientific contributions of Prof (Dr) PK Gupta in the field of toxicology. His research has focused on the toxicological profiling of chemicals, consumer products and plant sources, including investigations into their metabolic behavior in animal and human systems, and their implications for environmental and human health, with particular attention to effects on future generations.

Prof. Gupta has played a leading role in the development and application of short-term experimental methods to predict the long-term toxicological effects of chemicals. These methods have supported regulatory decision-making and contributed to the safer selection and use of chemicals in various sectors. His work has also addressed the emerging toxicological issues associated with nanotechnology, which enables the design of novel materials and devices at the nanoscale and presents new challenges for risk assessment and safety evaluation.

Throughout his career, Prof. Gupta has held several prominent positions, including Scientist-in-Charge of Safety Evaluation at IITR, Lucknow (formerly ITRC), Principal Scientist and Chief of the Division of Pharmacology & Toxicology at IVRI, Visiting Professor in the United States, and Advisor to the World Health Organization (Geneva). He has contributed extensively to toxicology education, the development of professional societies, and the establishment of scientific journals, including key roles in IUTOX, the Society of Toxicology (India), and Toxicology International.

In addition, Prof. Gupta has supervised numerous postgraduate and doctoral students who have progressed to leadership positions in academia, industry, and government. His work has had a lasting influence on the advancement of toxicological science and its application to public and environmental health.

Keywords

Toxicology; Veterinary Science; Environmental Health; Insecticide, Herbicide, Toxicity, Toxicokinetic, Reproductive Toxicology, Nanotoxicology, Education, Animal Welfare, Global Scientific Leadership. Pioneer Toxicologist, Distinguished Toxicologist, Dr PK Gupta, Dr Pawan Kumar Gupta

Introduction

In most scientific careers, researchers tend to remain within a single specialized domain. Professor (Dr) PK Gupta (Box) is a notable exception. Over the course of more than six decades, he continuously broadened and adapted his research interests to encompass emerging and interrelated areas of animal and human health, making significant contributions across multiple fields. His work has spanned dermatomycosis and the development of innovative techniques for toxicological profiling of pesticides, metals, petroleum products, phthalates, plant materials, and other commonly encountered chemicals. Through numerous successfully completed research projects, he advanced both methodology and application in toxicology.

While shifting research directions can be challenging, Prof. Gupta's intellectual curiosity, extensive engagement with international academic bodies, and regular access to leading scientific journals enabled him to remain at the forefront of emerging scientific trends. His personal library became a valuable academic resource for students and collaborators. His expertise and leadership led to frequent invitations to national and international conferences and symposia, where he regularly delivered invited lectures (Figure 2).

Recognized globally as a pioneer of modern toxicology in India, Prof. Gupta's work not only advanced scientific understanding but also elevated his department to international standards, contributing to the growth of toxicology as a discipline. He trained multiple generations of scientists, many of whom now occupy leadership positions in academia, industry, and government.

The development of modern toxicology in India is closely tied to the vision of a few institution-builders who combined scientific rigor with public purpose. Among them, Prof. Gupta stands out for the breadth of his scholarship, depth of mentorship, and the lasting impact of his institutional contributions. This article introduces his teaching philosophy, research innovations, leadership roles, and contributions to animal welfare and society, situated within the broader evolution of toxicology over the past six decades.

Research Metrics/ Achievements

Dr. Gupta's research outputs have been widely cited, with more than 1,800 citations and an h-index of 22 (ResearchGate, 2025 snapshot). His books are adopted as references in universities across India, USA, and Europe, reflecting his global academic impact. He has authored and co-authored more than 840+ peer-reviewed publications including reports, presentations and review articles, spanning topics from mechanistic toxicology to applied veterinary practice that integrates medicine and human health. His research primarily focuses on pesticide toxicology, agrochemicals, heavy metals, nanotoxicology and herbal

preparations in animals. He has advanced methodologies for studying toxicokinetic, dose-response relationships, and biochemical markers of toxicity. Achievements and advancement in research carried out during the period under review is summarized in Table 1. Details of the work carried out is listed under the reference section (ref: 1-117)

Box-1

Prof (Dr) P K Gupta, Pioneer Toxicologist of India, at the IUTOX Executive Meeting, 1980

Ph D (Toxicology), Post doctorate in Toxicology (USA), Hon DSc, PGDCA, FACVT (USA), FAEB, FST, FASc (AW), FNAVS

Formerly

Principal Scientist and Chief Division of Pharmacology and Toxicology, IVRI (1980-2003)

Scientist-In-charge Sponsored Projects Toxicology, Indian Institute of Toxicology Research (Formerly ITRC), Lucknow (1973-1980)

Advisor, World Health Organization (Geneva) (2003-2008)

Visiting Professor, University of Tennessee, USA (1977-1978)

Visiting Professor, West Virginia University, Morgan Town, USA (1978)

Research Officer, Department of Pharmacology, Post-graduate Institute of Medical Education & Research, Chandigarh, India (1967-68)

Sr Lecturer, Department of Biophysics, Punjab University, Chandigarh (1970-1973)

Founder Director, International Union of Toxicology, USA (1980-1983)

Past President (two times): Rotary Club District 3110 (1999-2000 and 2006-2007)

Founder President: Society of Toxicology India

Founder President: Academy of Sciences for Animal Welfare

Brief Bio

Professor (Dr) Pawan Kumar Gupta (born 14 February 1943, Punjab, India) is a pioneer in modern toxicology. He completed his school education up to grade 12 from the same place. Later, he completed his graduation (BVSc and AH); postgraduate (MVSc). and got first doctorate degree (PhD) in toxicology from Punjab/Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar/Ludhiana, India in 1965, 1967 and 1970, respectively. During his postgraduation he obtained advance training in dermatomycosis from All India Medical Sciences, New Delhi and in 1967 Joined Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, Chandigarh. Immediately after his PhD in the year 1970 he joined as senior lecturer in Punjab University, Chandigarh. In 1973, his expertise took him to globally known institute “Industrial Toxicology Research Institute (Now- Indian Institute of Toxicology Research, Lucknow) making the start of deep engagement in safety evaluation (Fig 1) . His expertise took him across continents to provide my expertise to known institutions in USA. After returning India joined Professor and Chief of the Division of Pharmacology and Toxicology from where he retired in 2003. His expensive experience played a pivotal role in guiding and providing expertise to United Nation’s Food and Agriculture (Rome); World Health Organization (Geneva); and International Atomic Energy Agency (Vienna). His experience has pivotal role to serve as advisor in guiding WHO for fixing ADI’s for various pesticides and other toxicants.

His groundbreaking work in the field of modern toxicology includes development of a minor surgical technique for the separation of urodeum and coprodeum, the main sections of the cloaca in poultry birds that allows the separation of urine and fecal matter. This procedure is extremely useful and has opened a new area of research to study toxicokinetic behavior of toxicants in birds (fate of chemicals). His another breakthrough research includes mechanism of action of various pesticides at the organ level and identification of higher toxic potential of alpha isomer of endosulfan and development of chronicity factors to use short- term tests to predict long term adverse effects of chemicals. His novel contributions published in peer review journals garnered him widespread recognition and appreciation by the scientific communities of the world. To share his knowledge and experience

Fig 1:

Prof PK Gupta (project-in-Charge) explained the importance of safety evaluation of chemicals for human health. Seen in the pic are (Dr PK Gupta, second from left, next to him is Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh, hon’ble Hemwati Nandan Bahuguna. Extreme right, Dr Sibte Hasan Zaidi, Director, IITR (then ITRC), next to him is Hon’ble President Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed and next Hon’ble UP Governor, Dr. Marri Chenna Reddy)

Development of New Techniques

A signature contribution of Professor (Dr) P. K. Gupta's research was the development of innovative experimental techniques that enhanced the precision and efficiency of toxicological investigations. Among these, the minor surgical technique to separate the urodeum and coprodeum—the principal chambers of the avian cloaca—stands out. This method enabled clean separation of urine and feces in poultry, allowing for precise kinetic and excretion studies. The resulting data improved dose–response modeling and residue analysis, providing a robust basis for regulatory decisions.

He also pioneered short-term biological assays designed to predict long-term toxic effects, sometimes referred to as 'chronicity factor' tests (Table 1). These approaches accelerated screening processes without compromising scientific rigor. Additionally, Prof. Gupta explored plant-based interventions, including neem-derived compounds, to mitigate metabolic disorders and ectoparasitic burdens, blending traditional knowledge with modern toxicological validation.

Toxicological Profiling

Prof. Gupta's research program systematically investigated the toxicological profiles of a broad range of substances: pesticides, herbicides, metals, phthalates, drugs, and Ayurvedic preparations. His team mapped organ- and system-level toxicities through comprehensive endpoints—clinical signs, hematological and biochemical markers, histopathology, and functional assessments (Table 1).

Noteworthy findings included isomer-specific toxicity comparisons (e.g., higher toxicity of alpha-endosulfan compared to other isomers) and structured evaluations of fungicides and herbicides relevant to both veterinary and environmental health. His work contributed substantially to safety evaluations and informed regulatory frameworks.

Metabolism and Toxicokinetic Behavior

Another cornerstone of Prof. Gupta's contributions was his extensive research on absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) of agrochemicals and other xenobiotics. Through radiolabeled studies—most notably with malathion—he elucidated metabolic pathways, tissue distribution, persistence, and residue levels (Table 1)

His work on endosulfan and endrin provided critical insights into persistence and bioaccumulation, informing surveillance protocols and withdrawal times that directly improved food safety standards. These toxicokinetic studies were pioneering in their methodological rigor and practical relevance to veterinary and environmental health.

Table 1

Research Achievements of Professor PK Gupta in different research areas

S. No	Active years	Research area	Brief Achievements
	1966	Dermatophyte infection	Advance training in human dermatophyte infection from All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi.
	1966-67	Investigation and treatment of Dermatophytes	Survey, identification, incidence and treatment in animals and human beings
	1967	Reproductive Problems	Investigation of reproductive problems in ladies
	1969	Development of Technique to study toxicokinetic behavior of drugs and chemicals in birds	development of a minor surgical technique for the separation of urodeum and coprodeum, the main sections of the cloaca in poultry birds that allows the separation of urine and fecal matter. This procedure is extremely useful in studying the fate of chemicals in birds and has opened a new area of research to study the fate of chemicals in birds.
	1969-1990	Pesticide Toxicity, toxicokinetic in birds	Toxicokinetic, bioavailability, and toxicological profile of pesticides
	1971-1973	Radiated and irradiated exposure in animals	Influence of Biochemical changes / toxicity and synergetic response, in pre-radiated animals, if any was investigated
	1973-1977	Safety Evaluation of Chemicals	Industrial sponsored chemicals/ pesticides for toxic potential (including all parameters as per requirement for the safe use of chemicals as per approved guidelines were undertaken). Industrial houses were advised for the steps to be taken while manufacturing pesticides or any other chemical.
	1969-1996	Toxicokinetic studies on pesticides and other drugs/chemicals	Using different pesticides, through toxicokinetic (TK) studies we could investigate how the body absorbs, distributes, metabolizes, and excretes a chemical or drug, specifically under conditions that cause toxicity. This provided us a vital link between the dose administered and the systemic exposure achieved within the body, making it a cornerstone of drug development and safety assessment. In addition, he could pin point that alpha isomer of endosulfan is more toxic than beta isomer.
	1978-1995	Reproductive and fetal abnormalities in animals exposed to herbicides insecticides and phthalates	Studies of reproductive and rate of fetal abnormalities studies using various pesticides have revealed a significant burden on animals. This can affect both society and families. Based on animal studies, it is essential to have a retrospective analysis of essential information about pregnant women, such as their pregnancy history and delivery details, is crucial for understanding the primary factors that influence pregnancy outcomes in women with fetal abnormalities.
	1990-1995	Indo-USSR Project on herbal products	Under Indo-USSR project, neem has been found to hypoglycemic agent and useful in diabetes, likewise. Likewise certain plants have been found to be useful as acaricide.
	1994-1996	Preparation of Indian Vet Pharmacopeia	Keeping in view the importance of vet drugs, it is for the first time Indian Vet Pharmacopeia has been prepared so that good standard drugs as per IP vet can be made available to farmers. This has now

			become an official publication by Drug Controller of India.
	1978-1992	Development of short term test to predict long term effects	Chronicity factor has been advised to assess and predict long term effects of any chemical. The newly developed test is extremely useful to detect long term effects of any chemical.
	1994-2003	Herbal/ayurvedic investigations (such as neem,) Mangifera and other plant based products)	Using and other plant extracts of Mangifera, studies were focused on its wide-ranging pharmacological properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-tumor, and many other problems including immunomodulatory activities

Reproductive Toxicity and Fetal Abnormalities

A sustained focus of Prof. Gupta's research has been on reproductive toxicology, especially maternal-fetal transfer and windows of developmental susceptibility (Table 1). His team investigated pesticide exposures during critical gestational periods, documenting teratogenic outcomes, fetal malformations, and subtle functional impairments that manifest postnatally. The work contributed to defining no-effect levels, identifying vulnerable developmental windows, and informing agricultural and veterinary guidelines to minimize fetal exposure to xenobiotics.

Environmental Health

Prof. Gupta's environmental toxicology research connected laboratory findings with real-world ecosystems. His studies linked exposure sources—including pesticides and industrial chemicals—to ecological effects, food contamination, and human-animal health. This research provided early warning signals and policy inputs, particularly in relation to One Health frameworks. Later, his work anticipated discussions on nanotoxicology, addressing exposure pathways, characterization issues, and risk management for nano-enabled products.

A successful Mentor

Professor Gupta's teaching philosophy was anchored in conceptual clarity, rigorous methodology, and ethical scientific practice. He emphasized that students must first learn to ask precise and meaningful scientific questions before selecting the appropriate methods. This intellectual discipline shaped generations of postgraduate and doctoral students, many of whom became leaders in research, education, and policy. His courses integrated interdisciplinary content—combining biostatistics, pathology, pharmacology, and environmental sciences—anticipating the One Health paradigm well before it gained widespread adoption. He prioritized hands-on training, real-world problem-solving, and clear communication of scientific uncertainty to build resilient and ethical scientists.

Mentorship for Prof Gupta was a lifelong commitment rather than a limited supervisory role. Over six decades, he mentored and inspired a large number of postgraduate and doctoral scholars. Many of these mentees went on to serve as Deans, Directors, Vice-Chancellors, and leaders in multinational corporations across India and abroad. His mentoring style combined rigorous scientific standards with personal encouragement, fostering independent thinking and leadership.

His impact as a mentor is reflected in the thriving academic and professional communities that continue to expand the scope of veterinary and environmental toxicology globally.

Editorial Responsibilities

Prof Gupta has the privilege to serve as the Editor-in-Chief of Three-volume set on Modern Toxicology; Advances in Environmental Toxicology and Health; and Toxicology International, a peer reviewed Journal 1994-2015. Honor to have served as book review Editor from 2002-2008, Marcel Dekker USA; Editorial Board, Member, Clinical Toxicology, Indian Journal of Pharmacology; Editor-in-Chief, Indian Journal of Toxicology.

Positions Held in Professional Societies

Prof Gupta has been lifetime Membership two dozen Societies: and held several key positions such as Director and Councilor, International Union of Toxicology (IUTOX), USA; 1980-1983, 1983-1986, IUTOX Nominating Committee member 1987-1990; Founder President, Society of Toxicology, India, 1979-1980, General Secretary, 1980-83., President, 1984-87, 1987-1990;; Executive Committee Member, All India Veterinary Scientists Association; Vice President, Academy of Environment Biology; 1980-1983, 2003-2006, FAO 1990, IAEA 1985-1990. President, Rotary International Rotary Club Mahaan, 1999-2000. In addition

Voracious Reader and Prolific Writer

Professor (Dr) P K Gupta possesses a remarkable thirst for knowledge combined with a strong commitment to scientific writing in emerging areas of toxicology. His contributions span textbooks, review articles, original research papers, reports, and popular science communications, serving both the student and teacher communities. Over the course of his distinguished career, he has authored more than 840 publications, including research papers, books, reviews, reports, book reviews, conference presentations, and articles for wider audiences.

Beginning in 1985 with the publication of his landmark three-volume set Modern Toxicology, Professor Gupta has authored and edited more than 20 books, many of which were published by leading international publishers such as Elsevier/Academic Press, Springer, Taylor & Francis, John Wiley, and CRC Press. His books cover a wide spectrum of subject areas, including veterinary

toxicology, pesticides in the Indian environment, advances in toxicology and environmental health, fundamental concepts in toxicology, problem-solving approaches, illustrative toxicology, nanotoxicology, and nanotechnology applications in veterinary medicine and livestock production (Table 2).

These textbooks are widely used and highly regarded among medical, veterinary, pharmaceutical, agricultural, environmental, and public health professionals, including academicians, industrial scientists, and students in India and abroad.

Beyond textbooks, Professor Gupta has produced a vast body of review articles, original research papers, and blogs addressing contemporary scientific issues relevant to students, teachers, and the public. As Founder and Editor-in-Chief of Toxicology International for more than two decades, he provided a respected platform for rigorous peer-reviewed scholarship, while also mentoring young researchers in scientific writing, peer review, and editorial ethics.

Leadership in Professional Societies

Prof. Gupta has played leadership roles in scientific societies and editorial initiatives that shaped the direction of toxicology in India and internationally (Fig 2). He served as Founder Director and Councilor of the International Union of Toxicology (IUTOX), Founder President of the Society of Toxicology (India), and Founder Editor-in-Chief of *Toxicology International*. He was a lifetime member of almost two dozen Societies, held several key positions such as Director and Councilor of International Union of Toxicology (IUTOX), USA; 1980-1983, 1983-1986, IUTOX Nominating Committee member 1987-1990; Founder President, Society of Toxicology, India, 1979-1980, General Secretary, 1980-83., President, 1984-87, 1987-1990;; Executive Committee Member, All India Veterinary Scientists Association; Vice President, Academy of Environment Biology and so on.

Global Engagements

Prof. Gupta's academic engagements extended far beyond India. He served as Visiting Scientist at the University of Tennessee in 1977, followed by postdoctoral research at West Virginia University, USA. Over subsequent decades, he delivered invited lectures and chaired scientific sessions in numerous countries including the United States, Ireland, England, Germany, Croatia, Russia, Thailand, Nepal and other countries. These experiences exposed his students and collaborators to international standards of Good Laboratory Practice (GLP), risk assessment frameworks, and regulatory toxicology, thereby raising the overall caliber of toxicological education in India.

His international collaborations facilitated harmonization of safety standards and enriched Indian academic ecosystems through knowledge exchange. He held advisory and consultant roles and contributed to curriculum reform, ethical

Table 2:**List of Books published by Prof PK Gupta**

Author / Editor	Title	Publisher (Place)	Year
Gupta, P.K.	Modern Toxicology, Basis of Organ and Reproduction Toxicity, Vol. 1	Metropolitan Book Company, New Delhi, India	1985
Gupta, P.K.	Modern Toxicology, Adverse Effects of Xenobiotics, Vol. 2	Metropolitan Book Company, New Delhi, India	1985
Gupta, P.K.	Modern Toxicology, Immuno and Clinical Toxicology, Vol. 3	Metropolitan Book Company, New Delhi, India	1985
Gupta, P.K.	Pesticides in the Indian Environment	Interprint, New Delhi	1986
Gupta, P.K.	Veterinary Toxicology	Cosmo Publications, New Delhi	1988
Gupta, P.K. & Raviprakash, V.	Advances in Toxicology: Selected Topics	Jagmander Book Agency, New Delhi	1988
Singh, Y.P. & Gupta, P.K.	Know Your Society	Society of Toxicology of India	1994
Gupta, P.K.	Modern Toxicology, Basis of Organ and Reproduction Toxicity, Vol. 1	Pharma Med Press (BSP Books Pvt. Ltd.), Hyderabad, India	2010
Gupta, P.K.	Modern Toxicology, Adverse Effects of Xenobiotics, Vol. 2	Pharma Med Press (BSP Books Pvt. Ltd.), Hyderabad, India	2010
Gupta, P.K.	Modern Toxicology, Immuno- and Clinical Toxicology, Vol. 3	Pharma Med Press (BSP Books Pvt. Ltd.), Hyderabad, India	2010
Gupta, P.K.	Essential Concepts in Toxicology — Compendium for Pharmacy, Medical	Pharma Med Press, Hyderabad	2014
Gupta, P.K.	Fundamentals of Toxicology: Essential Concepts and Applications	Elsevier, USA. ISBN: 978-0-12-805426-0	2016
Gupta, P.K.	Toxicology: Resource for Self-Study Questions (Kindle Edition)	Kindle Publications/ Amazon	2018
Gupta, P.K.	Illustrative Toxicology with Study Questions	Elsevier, USA. ISBN: 978-0-12-813213-5	2018
Gupta, P.K.	Concepts and Applications in Veterinary Toxicology: An Interactive Guide	Springer Nature, Switzerland	2019
Gupta, P.K.	Toxicology: Resource for Self-Study Questions (2nd Ed, Kindle Edition)	Kindle Publications/ Amazon	2020
Gupta, P.K.	Problem Solving Questions in Toxicology: A Study Guide for the Board and Other Examinations	Springer Nature, Switzerland	2020
Gupta, P.K. (Contributor)	Principles of Toxicology in Brain Storming Questions in Toxicology	Francis and Taylor, CRC Press	2020
Gupta, P.K.	Fundamentals of Nanotoxicology	Elsevier, USA. ISBN: 9780323903998	2022
Gupta, P.K.	Nanotoxicology of Nanobiomedicine	Springer Nature, Switzerland	2023
Gupta, P.K.	Nanotechnology of Veterinary Medicine and Livestock Production	Elsevier / Academic Press, USA	2025

Fig 2
Prof PK Gupta, Founder Director of IUTOX during meetings held in Belgium (1980), Ireland (1981) and Sandiego (1983)

guidelines, and scientific communication standards across multiple National and International institutions such as WHO (Geneva), FAO (Rome), and IAEA (Vienna); 1980-1983, 2003-2006, FAO 1990, IAEA 1985-1990 (Fig 3).

Fig 3:

Prof PK Gupta's role as Expert Consultant in United Nations FAO (Rome), WHO (Geneva) and IAEA (Vienna)

Honors and Recognitions

Prof Gupta is recipient of several (200+) global and national awards including gold medals, lifetime awards, merit awards, IVRI-ICAR best teacher award, IVA best research reward, Astra-Zeneca and SOT, USA (2004), LIMCA Book of Award (2019) and UP Book of Records award (2018). Prof Gupta has over 55 years of experience of training, teaching, research and management in modern toxicology. His students are spread globally and have shown excellent performance in teaching, research, industries and management institutions. He has biographies in world renowned publications houses such as in Marquis Who's Who (USA), IBC (UK), etc. These accolades highlight his multifaceted impact across research, teaching, and leadership (Fig 4).

Organization of Conferences and Symposia

Professor Gupta's has shown his excellent ability in organizing conferences, symposia, and other events both at national and international levels. His expertise and as the primary role to create a structure that facilitates the exchange of knowledge, professional development, and networking among individuals with shared interests is an excellent one. This involved defining objectives, planning logistics like venue and program, securing speakers and sponsors, managing participant registration, promoting the event, and overseeing the entire execution from planning to post-event evaluation. During his tenure as patron of the society he has the ability to organize 35 conferences and symposia including one 2nd congress of toxicology in developing countries in different parts of the country (Fig 5).

Fig 4
Professor PK Gupta is recipient of National and International Awards

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Fig 5

2nd Congress of Toxicology of Developing Countries held in 1991 in Delhi (First Picture: seen in the picture are extreme left Prof PK Gupta on extreme right and in second row, Hon'ble Minister of Forest and Environment Shri Kamal Nath (in the middle). In the second picture, seen in the picture in Front row from extreme right, Prof PK Gupta, Dr PK Ray and Hon'ble Minister of Forest and Environment Shri Kamal Nath.

Animal Welfare Program and Ethical Science

Through the Academy of Sciences for Animal Welfare, Professor (Dr) P K Gupta has been a strong advocate for humane science and animal protection. Under his guidance, the Academy promotes the principles of the 3Rs — Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement — to ensure ethical practices in animal research. It provides veterinary care and community outreach programs, including castration and anti-rabies vaccination of stray dogs, thereby improving both animal and public health. The Academy also emphasizes scientific integrity, ethical review mechanisms, and responsible use of animals in experimentation, aligning its initiatives with global standards for humane and ethical science.

Social Activities

Professor (Dr) P K Gupta has been deeply engaged in social and humanitarian service through his long-standing association with the Rotary Clubs of Bareilly North, Mahaan and Vishal. As a committed Rotarian, he has worked tirelessly to promote compassion, education, and welfare for the community — particularly the poor, underprivileged, and elderly. His initiatives have included book and material donations to under-resourced children, health and welfare programs for senior citizens, and community outreach activities aimed at uplifting disadvantaged groups.

Serving as President of Rotary International District 3110 during 1999–2000 and 2006–2007, Professor Gupta played a pivotal role in polio eradication campaigns, educational support projects, and welfare programs for public servants and marginalized individuals. His leadership and dedication to service were recognized with six awards for exemplary community and humanitarian contributions.

Fig Prof Gupta Honored and awarded for social services for eradication of polio and to provide social service to sick and old senior citizens

Fig 6:
Prof Gupta Honored for social services

Current Roles

Prof. Gupta continues to serve as Director of the Toxicology Consulting Group and President of the Academy of Sciences for Animal Welfare. He remains actively involved in advisory work, manuscript development, and mentorship of early-career scientists.

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